

Surface Coverage of Surfactants on the DME in the Polarographic Reduction of Anthraquinone Derivatives

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The adsorption properties of SAS on the DME are studied in aqueous buffer solutions of different pH by the electrocapillary curves in absence and presence of some anthraquinone derivatives. The latter displays some adsorption properties which are also studied. The degree of coverage, θ , of the adsorbed SAS on DME are determined in absence and presence of the depolarizers.

THE polarographic reduction of anthraquinone derivatives was studied by various authors^{1,2}. The effects of surface active substances (SAS) on the polarographic reduction of anthraquinone derivatives in aqueous buffer solutions of different pH was studied qualitatively by Hammam *et al*³, in course of the polarographic determination of such compounds. No work has yet been done on the evaluation of the quantities of SAS which are adsorbed and cover the electrode surface during the electroreduction of anthraquinone derivatives. The aim of the present study is to make use of the electrocapillary curves as a method for the quantitative determination of the surface coverage of SAS on the d.m.e. during the electroreduction of some anthraquinone derivatives.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The compounds used in the present investigation are

- I (AS) : $R_8 = \text{SO}_3\text{H}$; $R_1, R_2, R_4, R_5, R_6, R_7$ and $R_8 = \text{H}$.
 II (AAS) : $R_1 = \text{NH}_2$; $R_8 = \text{SO}_3\text{H}$;
 R_2, R_4, R_6, R_7 and $R_8 = \text{H}$.
 III (AZRS) : $R_1 = R_2 = \text{OH}$; $R_8 = \text{SO}_3\text{H}$;
 R_4, R_5, R_6, R_7 and $R_8 = \text{H}$.
 IV (QS) : $R_1 = R_4 = \text{OH}$; $R_8 = \text{SO}_3\text{H}$;
 R_2, R_5, R_6, R_7 and $R_8 = \text{H}$.
 V (AZSB) : $R_1 = R_2 = \text{OH}$; $R_4 = R_6 = \text{NH}_2$; $R_5 = R_8 = \text{SO}_3\text{H}$;
 $R_3 = R_7 = \text{H}$.
 VI (AZV) : $R_1 = R_4 = \text{NH}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{SO}_3\text{H}$; $R_7 = R_8 = \text{OH}$;
 R_2, R_5, R_6 and $R_8 = \text{H}$.

Stock solutions ($10^{-3} M$) of the compounds were prepared in double distilled water. 1-5% solutions of the SAS, Triton X-100 and sodium dodecylbenzene sulphonate (DDBSO₃Na), were prepared in double distilled water.

Working procedure and apparatus :

The working procedure and apparatus were the same as described earlier¹, using the LP 60 polarograph. The procedure essentially was the measurements of the drop time at different potentials for 10 ml de-aerated $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ solution of the compounds in buffer solution as such, or after the addition of 0.05-0.65 ml of the SAS. The capillary characteristics were flow rate (m)=2.4 mg sec⁻¹ and drop time (t)=3.5 sec at a mercury height (h)=38 cm Hg (in 0.1 M KCl, open circuit). All experiments were performed at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

The important parameter in electrode kinetics is the degree of coverage θ of the electrode by the adsorbed substance. This quantity is given by the formula⁵

$$\theta = \frac{\Gamma}{\Gamma_m}$$

where Γ stands for the quantity of substance adsorbed (mole cm⁻²) at a given bulk concentration and Γ_m the quantity adsorbed when the surface is saturated. The dependence of Γ on potential can be obtained from the electrocapillary curves (ecc), in which the adsorption of the surface-active substances is indicated by a decrease in the surface tension at the dropping mercury electrode. For this purpose the Gibbs adsorption equation⁶⁻⁹ is used

$$\Gamma = -\frac{d\gamma}{RT \ln C_A}$$

where γ is the surface tension (dyne cm⁻¹), C_A is the concentration of the adsorbed substance in the solution (mole l⁻¹), R the gas constant and T the absolute temperature. The surface tension at the mercury electrode can be obtained from the drop time which are obtained from the relation :

$$\gamma = \frac{mg}{2\pi r_0 t}$$

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Fig. 1. Electrocapillary curves of different concentrations of SAS in aqueous buffer solutions.

g is the gravitational constant (cm. sec^{-2}), r_0 internal diameter of the capillary.

Effect of SAS on the ecm in absence of depolarizer :

The ecc obtained for different concentration of SAS in buffer solutions of different pH are shown in Fig. 1. The surfactants (SAS) used are non-ionic Triton X-100 and anionic dodecylamine perchlorate. They give a precipitate in solutions of the depolarizer. The results obtained indicate that the effect of adsorption of SAS on the surface tension differs with changing electrode potentials.

With Triton X-100, the addition of small quantities of SAS ($7.39 \times 10^{-5} M$) causes a decrease of the interfacial tension γ at the mercury electrode. The decrease in γ in acid solutions is lower than in alkaline ones. Also the shift of electrocapillary maxima (ecm) to less negative potentials increases in the same direction.

In case of DDBSO₃Na, there is a large decrease in surface tension with small quantities of the SAS. Successive increase in concentration decreases the surface tension and shift the ecm slightly to more negative potentials.

Adsorption property of the anthraquinone derivatives :

A comparison of the values of γ corresponding to the ecm in absence and presence of the depolarizer

shows that the value of γ in presence of the depolarizer is less than that in its absence, denoting that the latter has an adsorption effect which slightly retards the penetration of SAS in the electrode double layer. This adsorption is supported from the values of x (> 0.5) in the relation $i_e = kh^x$, and also by the fact that the compounds under investigation display some surface active properties⁸. The relative absorbability of the depolarizer is discussed below.

In presence of the same concentration of the depolarizer the values of γ for the same concentration of SAS in acid medium in case of Triton X-100 are in the order $V < III < VI < II < I$ but in DDBSO₃Na the order is $V < IV < III < VI < II < I$. In alkaline medium, γ for Triton X-100 increases in the order $V < VI < IV < II < III < I$ but with DDBSO₃Na it is $IV < V < III < VI < II < I$. This behaviour indicates generally that in acid medium the adsorption of II and I is high while that of V and III or IV is low. In alkaline media, V, IV and VI exhibit low adsorption properties.

Effect of SAS on the ecm in presence of depolarizer :

The ecc of $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ anthraquinone derivatives in buffer solution in presence of different concentrations of Triton X-100 and DDBSO₃Na are shown in Fig. 2. Addition of the compounds at $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ to a buffer solution decreases the surface tension of

Fig. 2. Electrocapillary curves of anthraquinone derivatives in presence of SAS at different pH.

the mercury electrode and shifts the ecm to more negative potentials. Low concentrations of Triton X-100 shift the ecm back to less negative ones and both cause a decrease of the surface tension. This shift in potential increases with increasing concentration of SAS. DDBSO_3Na causes slight splitting of the ecm (as observed in the case of V) with increasing concentration. This indicates that DDBSO_3Na retards the reduction process and increases the overvoltage more than Triton X-100. The shift in ecm by Triton X-100 to less negative values is more apparent in acidic than in alkaline media whereas the retardation of DDBSO_3Na in alkaline medium is more than that of Triton X-100. This behaviour is attributed to the fact that the depolarizer and DDBSO_3Na in alkaline media exist as anions but DDBSO_3Na being of higher surface activity would be more adsorbed at the d.m.e. The negative charge of depolarizer and SAS also favours the repulsion of the depolarizer from the electrode surface.

The values of θ (Tables 1 and 2) indicate that the coverage of the electrode surface by the anionic or non-ionic surfactant increases with the pH of solution, i.e., the adsorption of SAS increases with the alkalinity of the medium. This is supported by the higher decrease in the γ value in alkaline than in acid media at the same concentration of SAS. In alkaline medium the reducible materials exist as anions, hence the anionic or non-ionic SAS is more adsorbed than the depolarizer species. The increase

in adsorption of SAS with pH of solution is supported from the values of θ obtained in absence of the anthraquinone derivatives, where the degree of coverage increases with rise of pH of the solution in case of anionic DDBSO_3^- . With Triton X-100, the θ value relatively decreases with the pH in absence of the depolarizer indicating that the neutral form of SAS in this state is adsorbed slightly in alkaline medium.

Generally, the value of θ in presence of the depolarizer is smaller than in its absence. This indicates that anthraquinone derivatives exhibit a

TABLE 1—SURFACE COVERAGE OF THE d.m.e. BY TRITON X-100 IN PRESENCE OF 5×10^{-4} M ANTHRAQUINONE DERIVATIVES

Compound	pH	Slope $= \Gamma RT$	$\Gamma \times 10^{-7}$ mole cm^{-2}	θ $\times 10^{-11}$
I	2.5	10200	8.093	3.09
	10.1	21000	8.337	3.10
II	2.5	18400	7.300	2.91
	10.1	14000	5.558	2.25
III	3.4	14800	5.875	2.57
	10.1	24000	9.528	3.73
IV	7.0	12000	4.764	2.02
	11.0	14400	5.716	—
V	3.6	8400	3.330	1.39
	7.02	10200	4.049	1.74
VI	10.55	14000	5.558	2.41
	2.5	13000	5.161	1.93
	10.1	18000	7.146	6.86

TABLE 2—SURFACE COVERAGE OF THE d.m.e. BY DDBSO₃Na IN PRESENCE OF 5×10^{-4} M OF ANTHRAQUINONE DERIVATIVES

Compound	pH	Slope = Γ/RT	$\Gamma \times 10^{-7}$ mole cm ⁻²	θ $\times 10^{-12}$
I	2.5	16000	6.325	2.39
	10.1	24400	9.680	3.70
II	2.5	14400	5.716	2.20
	10.1	19000	7.543	2.91
III	3.4	18400	7.30	—
	10.1	18400	7.30	2.85
IV	4.1	56000	2.223	—
	11.4	16400	6.510	2.81
V	3.7	18000	7.140	3.13
	7.02	14000	5.558	2.37
VI	10.25	24000	9.520	4.05
	2.5	8000	3.176	1.21
	10.1	11000	4.360	1.64

TABLE 3—SURFACE COVERAGE OF THE d.m.e. BY SAS IN ABSENCE OF THE DEPolarizer

Triton X-100				DDBSO ₃ Na			
pH	Slope	$\Gamma \times 10^{-7}$ mole cm ⁻²	θ $\times 10^{-12}$	pH	Slope	$\Gamma \times 10^{-7}$ mole cm ⁻²	θ $\times 10^{-12}$
3.4	19000	7.543	3.27	4.1	20400	8.098	3.49
7.0	15600	6.143	2.65	7.0	17000	6.745	2.86
11.4	13600	5.399	2.33	11.4	422400	8.892	3.80

certain tendency for adsorption on the electrode surface and take some part in the electric double layer, hence slightly retarding the penetration of the adsorbed SAS.

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